

Graphene-based Nanomaterials Integration with Bioreceptors for Enhanced Point-of-Care Diagnostics and Environmental Sensors

Marianna Rossetti¹, Ruslan Alvarez-Diduk¹, Andy Bruno¹, Davi Marques,¹ Gabriel Maroli,¹ Yi-Fan Liang,¹ Ana Ameda², Sadik Cenolli², Lueda Kulla², Nevila Broli², Majlinda Vasjari,² Arben Merkoçi^{1,3}

¹ *Nanobioelectronics & Biosensors Group, Catalan Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology (ICN2), CSIC and BIST, Campus UAB, Bellaterra, Barcelona, Spain.*

² *Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Natural Sciences, University of Tirana, Albania.*

³ *ICREA Institució Catalana de Recerca i Estudis Avançats, Barcelona, Spain*

We explore the use of graphene-based nanomaterials combined with bioreceptors to develop advanced Point-of-Care and environmental monitoring devices. We produce nanostructured electrodes through an eco-friendly, cost-effective, one-step printing/stamping technique. Utilizing an infrared laser, we achieve precise fabrication of highly exfoliated reduced graphene oxide (rGO) decorated in situ with gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) via instantaneous laser-induced co-reduction of graphene oxide (GO) and gold cations (Au³⁺). These nanocomposites can be transferred onto flexible substrates like PET or nitrocellulose [1]. The produced electrode can be functionalized with DNA probes, aptamers, antibodies [2], or nanobodies through various chemical methods for the specific detection of target nucleic acids, proteins, or small molecules. Binding events between immobilized bioreceptors and target analytes cause detectable changes in the electrochemical signal, enabling rapid and sensitive detection of biomarkers or environmental pollutants. The inclusion of AuNPs on the rGO surface enhances electrochemical performance by increasing the number of active sites, thereby improving sensitivity in biosensor applications, while the biorecognition elements provide high specificity. This integration of highly specific bioreceptors, graphene-based nanomaterials and electrochemical techniques represents a promising strategy for point-of-care applications ranging from environmental monitoring to health diagnostics.

References

[1] A. Scroccarello, R. Álvarez-Diduk, F. Della Pelle, C. de Carvalho Castro e Silva, A. Idili, C. Parolo, D. Compagnone, A. Merkoçi. *ACS Sensors*, **8**, 598 (2023).

[2] D. Echeverri, E. Calucho, J. Marrugo-Ramírez, R. Álvarez-Diduk, J. Orozco, A. Merkoçi, *Biosensors and Bioelectronics*, **252**, 116142 (2024).

Acknowledgments

This project is partly funded from the European Union's Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2021–2027) under grant agreement No 101120706 (2D-BioPAD), from the HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-02-01 under grant agreement No 101059266 (SUSNANO), and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101029884 (SERENA). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The ICN2 is funded by the CERCA programme/Generalitat de Catalunya, supported by the Severo Ochoa Centres of Excellence programme, Grant CEX2021-001214-S, funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039.501100011033. We acknowledge Departament de Recerca i Universitats of Generalitat de Catalunya for the grant 2021 SGR 01464 and Grant PID2021-124795NB-I00 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by “ERDF A way of making Europe”.